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PROGRAM & ABSTRACTS BOOK

THE 4th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
PHARMACEUTICAL AND CLINICAL RESEARCH
(4th ICPCR)

*Treatment for Non Communicable Disease:
From Bench to Bed*

November 16-17, 2023

CO HOST

IN COLLABORATION WITH

UNIVERSITY
OF MALAYA

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Program and Abstract Book

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***"Treatment for Non Communicable Disease:
From Bench to Bed"***

**November 16-17, 2023
MEDAN**

Host:
Faculty of Pharmacy
Universitas Sumatera Utara
Medan-Indonesia

Co-Host:
Institut Kesehatan Helvetia, Medan, Indonesia
Universitas Tjut Nyak Dhien, Medan, Indonesia
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EFFECTIVENESS TESTING OF THE COMBINATION OF ETHANOL EXTRACT OF RED GINGER (*Zingiber officinal var. rubred*) AND TURMERIC (*Curcuma domestica Val.*) AS ANTIBACTERIAL ON BACTERIAL GROWTH *Escherichia coli*

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to determine the combination of ethanol extract of red ginger and turmeric capable of inhibiting the growth of *Escherichia coli* bacteria and to determine the best concentration of a combination of red ginger and turmeric extracts in inhibiting *Escherichia coli* bacteria.

Methods: Combination of red ginger and turmeric was extracted using the maceration method with 96% ethanol solvent. The antibacterial effectiveness test was carried out by disc diffusion method with 7 samples from each treatment group, a combination of 40% red ginger extract and 0% turmeric, 30% red ginger extract and 10% turmeric, 20% red ginger extract and 20% turmeric, 20% red ginger extract, and 20% turmeric extract. 10% red ginger and 30% turmeric, 0% red ginger extract, and 40% turmeric.

Results: The results of the study showed that the inhibitory effect of 40% red ginger and 0% turmeric was 17,6 mm, 30% red ginger and 10% turmeric inhibition was 14,3 mm, and 20% red ginger and 20% turmeric inhibition 12,1 mm, concentration of 10% red ginger and 30% turmeric inhibition of 9,1 mm, concentration of 0% red ginger and 40% turmeric inhibition of 15,9 mm.

Conclusion: From this study the combination of red ginger and turmeric ethanol extract had an inhibitory effect on *Escherichia coli* bacteria at a concentration of 40% red ginger and 0% turmeric which was included in the strong category of 17.6 mm.

Keywords: red ginger, turmeric, *Escherichia coli*, Antibacterial.